

Word Pairs – Coding Scheme

Group	Category	Variant 1	Variant 2	Variant 1 Adopted	Variant 2 Adopted
group_1	noun	thermos bottle	vacuum flask	thermos bottle; thermos; bottle	vacuum flask; flask; vacuum
group_1	noun	gift	present	gift	present
group_1	noun	cup	mug	cup	mug
group_1	verb	to fix	to repair	fix; to fix; fixes; fixed; fixing	repair; to repair; repairs; repaired; repairing
group_1	verb	to look at	to examine	look; to look at; looks at; looked at; looking at; looks; looked; looking	examine; to examine; examines; examined; examining
group_1	verb	to put up	to install	put; to put up; puts up; put up; putting up; puts; putting	install; to install; installs; installed; installing
group_1	adjective	colorful	multicolored	colorful; colourful	multicolored; multicoloured; multi-colored; multi-coloured; multi-colour; multicolour; multicolor
group_1	adjective	cracked	fractured	cracked	fractured
group_1	adjective	spotted	dotted	spotted; with [...] spots; spotty; with spots	dotted; with [...] dots; with dots
group_2	noun	beanie	knit hat	beanie	knit; hat; knit hat; knitted hat; knitted
group_2	noun	couch	sofa	couch	sofa
group_2	noun	merry-go-round	carousel	merry-go-round; merry go round; merrygoround	carousel
group_2	verb	to jump over	to hop over	jump; to jump over; jump over; jumps over; jumped over; jumping over; jumps; jumped; jumping	hop; to hop over; hop over; hops over; hopped over; hopping over; hops; hopped; hopping
group_2	verb	to hug	to embrace	hug; to hug; hugs; hugged; hugging	embrace; to embrace; embraces; embraced; embracing
group_2	verb	to cut	to chop	cut; to cut; cuts; cutting	chop; to chop; chops; chopped; chopping
group_2	adjective	shiny	glossy	shiny; shinier; shiniest; shine	glossy; glossier; glossiest; gloss
group_2	adjective	round	circular	round; rounder; roundest; rounded	circular; circle; more circular; most circular
group_2	adjective	plaid	checkered	plaid	checkered; checked; chequered